

COMMON FACTORS OF NECK PAIN:

Neck pain can affect people's lives badly whatever it social or personal life. When they have this type of chronic neck pain, they are unable to enjoy their lives. Additionally, it can also diminish their work productivity.

Neck pain may be caused by an injury or trauma or due to any other health conditions. Visit [Neck Center](#), if you are suffering from chronic neck pain.

What Are Common Causes Of Neck Pain?

The main causes of neck pain are given below:

It is observed that neck pain is more common in women compared to men. Also, people with a family history of neck pain are prone to it. People who are psychologically diagnosed with anxiety and depression are more at risk. Such type of chronic pain requires treatment at **Neck Center Nj**.

Injury and Accidents:

If people have a common neck injury known as whiplash may suffer from chronic neck pain. When the head is forced to move back or forth in the advanced range of motion, this rapid movement can cause damage to the muscles and ligaments. This may result in pain and

stiffness. Usually, whiplash is caused by a car accident or a trauma from a sports accident, or a sudden fall from height.

Nerve Compression:

When a patient's cervical nerve becomes compressed, leading to a radiating pain that may move up into the head, behind the eyes, into the jaw, down the arms. Basically, the main cause of nerve compression is herniated discs. Moreover, bone spurs may also cause compressed nerves.

Health Conditions:

- **Osteoarthritis:** it is known as spondylosis if it occurs in spinal facet joints. Spinal facet joints are a common form of arthritis that is caused by wear and tear and overage. Moreover, it becomes the main reason for osteophytes that mass the spinal canal and compress nerve roots in the neck.

- **Other Kinds of Arthritis:** Since there are many types of arthritis, particularly the inflammatory forms like rheumatoid arthritis, ankylosing spondylitis, psoriatic arthritis, and juvenile idiopathic arthritis, can damage the cervical spine. Chronic inflammation in the neck creates the destruction of the joints that support movement in the neck.
- **Other Disease Processes:** However, neck pain is most commonly produced by strain, extended pain, and/or neurologic deficiency may be evidence of something more dangerous. These indications should not be neglected. Spinal infection, spinal cord compression, tumor, fracture, and other disorders can happen. If you have experienced a head injury, your neck is expected to be affected, too. Seek medical attention promptly.

Lifestyle Issues:

- **Extra weight:** Additional pounds put unjust weight on the spine and powerless abs can neglect to help it, the two of which may disturb the spine's equilibrium and cause the neck to twist forward to compensate.
- **Stress:** if you have anxiety or stress, maybe grasping the muscles that move your neck without realizing it, possibly leading to a hard, sore neck.
- **Poor Posture:** Extended wrong body posture when using a smartphone or working on a computer or tablet excessively can lead to neck pain.
- Moreover, “Clenched teeth, improper lifting, prolonged periods of sitting at the computer, and reading in bed may exaggerate neck pain.

Seek medical attention at [Neck Center New Jersey](#), if you are suffering from extensive neck pain.